

Fixes for working with Snakemake Group Jobs

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

Fixes for working with group jobs

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Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

Several issues related to group jobs have been fixed.

First, when executing a group job - a set of rules - in a remote environment, the outputs are sent only after all rules had finished. A fix was implemented to ensure that outputs are sent in the correct order, so that the timestamps of the files in remote storage correspond to the order of execution.

During the hackathon, a `nodeLocal` flag was introduced for files that are local to the remote execution environment. A fix was suggested that ensures these files are not sent to or retrieved from remote storage when a default remote storage provider is used; this fix is currently a work in progress.

To improve the debugging experience for group jobs, dry-run mode has been fixed to display the same Snakemake output as a live run when group jobs are utilized.

Associated Project Workitems

- [fix the order of output upload to remote storage for group jobs](#)
- [update the `nodeLocal` option to allow for temporary files during remote execution that are not sent to cloud storage](#)
- [group jobs are displayed on dryrun](#)

Acknowledgement

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